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LOCKDOWN: A TIME FOR NATURE TO REJUVENATE ITSELF

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ABSTRACT

Pollution in the form of air and water in the environment generates many socio-economic problems among the humans population. Impurities are not come from regular activities but also form religious activities. Both form causes many direct and indirect medical problems in humans especially lungs diseases and gastrointestinal complications, sometime these leads to death. As nature maintain itself, it regularly rejuvenate itself time to time but due to coronavirus pandemic, lockdown of cities occurs all over the world so the people in home not on the road, the air pollution level decrease and nature has time to clear itself. Itself cleaning process of nature ultimately beneficial for us, we can survive only in healthy and clean environment not in polluted.

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INTRODUCTION

Fresh and healthy air is essential for both plants and animals prolong exposure of impure air has significant effect on both of them. There are many anthropogenic activities like combustion of fuel for production, construction, agriculture; deforestation releases various gases in atmosphere, which increases pollution level. Air Pollution in cities increases very quickly due to regular use of fossil fuel in generation of power, transportation, industrial needs and other activities as compare to villages. Prolong exposure of air pollutants SPM, RSPM, SO₂, CO, and NO₂ can cause cardiovascular and respiratory disease. (Patel et.al. 2017). In cities the main air pollutants are particulate matter (PM), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), and ozone (O₃). The common sources these pollutants are vehicles, manufacturing industries, construction activities, road dust, waste burning, combustion of coal, oil and biomass etc.

Air Quality Index (AQI)

Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) has recognised 12 parameter for Indian National Air Quality Standards (INAQS) includes carbon monoxide (CO) nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter (PM) < 2.5 microns size (PM_{2.5}), PM <10 microns size (PM₁₀), Ozone (O₃), Lead (Pb), Ammonia (NH₃), Benzo(a)Pyrene (BaP), Benzene (C₆

H₆), Arsenic (As), and Nickel (Ni). The eight parameters [carbon monoxide (CO) nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), particulate matter (PM) of less than 2.5 microns size (PM_{2.5}), PM of less than 10 microns size (PM₁₀), Ozone (O₃), Lead (Pb), Ammonia (NH₃), Ammonia (NH₃)] have short-term standards (like 1 hours /8 hours /24 hours) and annual standards (except for CO and O₃) whereas other four parameters [Benzo(a)Pyrene (BaP), Benzene (C₆ H₆), Arsenic (As), and Nickel (Ni)] have only annual standards. (CPCB, 2014). Recently, air pollution has considered as a public health problem at global level. According to World Health Organization, it is a major environmental health hazard produced by different sources around the world. As per WHO report, both indoor and outdoor air pollution were responsible for 3.7 million deaths of people aged under 60 in 2012. The level of PM 2.5 and PM 10 (Air-borne particles smaller than 2.5 micrometers in diameter and 10 micrometers in diameter) and level of carcinogenic chemicals like Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂) and Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) have increases drastically in recent years in most cities of India, creating risk problem of respiratory diseases and other health complication especially in women and children among the population (Table-2 and Table-3).

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Table 1 Various Categories of IND-Air Quality Index (National Air Quality Index, CPCB, 2014)

Category	Range
Good	0-50
Satisfactory	51-100
Moderately Polluted	101 - 200
Poor	201 - 300
Very poor	301 - 400
Severe	401 - 500

Table 2 Projected health impacts at global level

Diseases Respiratory diseases (million number of cases)	Years	
	2010	2060
Bronchitis in children aged 6 to 12	12	36
Chronic bronchitis (adults, cases)	4	10

Source: OECD Policy highlights the economic consequences of outdoor air pollution, 2016

Table 3 Health Statements for AQI Categories (CPCB, 2014)

AQI	Associated Health Impacts
Good(0-50)	Minimal Impact
Satisfactory (51-100)	May cause minor breathing discomfort to sensitive people
Moderately polluted (101-200)	May cause breathing discomfort to the people with lung disease such as asthma and discomfort to people with heart disease, children and older adults
Poor (201-300)	May cause breathing discomfort to people on prolonged exposure and discomfort to people with heart disease
Very Poor (301-400)	May cause respiratory illness to the people on prolonged exposure. Effect may be more pronounced in people with lung and heart diseases
Severe (401-500)	May cause respiratory effects even on healthy people and serious health impacts on people with lung/heart diseases. The health impacts may be experienced even during light physical activity

As per WHO (2014), New Delhi had bad atmospheric air of 1,600 cities around the world. 13 cities of India in the 20 cities with the highest level of PM_{2.5}; New Delhi having a PM_{2.5} level of 153, six times higher than safe limit of 25. Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study (GBD), reported that air pollution was the second largest risk factor for emerging new disease among peoples after malnutrition from 1990 to 2016 (ISLDBIAPC, 2018 & 2019).

World Health Organization (2014) listed 37 cities of India in top 100 cities of world for having worst PM₁₀, especially cities like Delhi, Raipur, Gwalior, and Lucknow are listed in the category of top 10 (Guttikunda et.al., 2014). World health organization (WHO) reported 7 million deaths in world due to air pollution both in 2012 alone (WHO, 2015). Lim *et al.*, (2012) reported that the Indian cities are among the most polluted areas in the world and air pollution cause deaths of approximately 670,000 people annually (TERI, 2015).

21 Days Lockdown in India

India is the biggest democratic country in the world. It is the home of 1.3 billion people. Due to pandemic coronavirus infection in the world, Indian Government decided to complete lockdown all states for 21 days (from 25 March to 14 April, 2020) to prevent infection among our people. With the large

number, there are more chance of pollution both air and water due to which India always have their position in top ten polluted (Air) cities in th world. Developing countries like India, has air pollution issue due to large number of vehicles on the road , regular construction works (building, homes) and different sector of factories. As the lockdown announced these activities are restricted for 21 days and recently the level of air pollution in India drop quickly. Similar the pollution levels decreases were also seen in different part of world like Europe, USA and China.

The Pawan Gupta, senior scientist, Earth Sciences of Universities Space Research Association, NASA's Marshall Space Flight Center said "It is true that pollution levels are going down and will continue to be lower as a result of lockdown". He also said that "Rain is a very effective aerosol removal process from the atmosphere and can bring down particulate matter values,". The heavy rains occurs in the north and west part of country, helped to remove pollutants from air (Jordan, 2020). After a lockdown, air quality in New Delhi has drooped to satisfactory level form very poor or severe. The lockdown notification shut down the both private and government offices (except necessary sector) schools, colleges, universities, malls, markets, cinema theatres and non-essential service sector. All form of transport like bus, trains, metro and domestic and international flight has been stopped for people.

As the capital of India, New Delhi have been very busy lifestyle for that regular mode of transport like vehicles, bus, train and flight release smog in the air used by many people, the air pollution level have dropped from 91 micrograms per cubic meter (unhealthy) (March, 20, 2020) to 26 micrograms per cubic meter (March 27, 2020) due to complete lockdown. Central Pollution Control Board of India's has revealed on the basis of recoded data that the air pollution level decreases 71% in nitrogen dioxide levels. It has also state that the pollution level drops in Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata and Bangalore. Kuldeep Srivastava, Heads the regional meteorological center at the Indian Meteorological Department said that "the air quality is likely to slip into 'good' category soon. It is due to reduced vehicular traffic and rise in temperature," (Jordan, 2020). System of Air Quality and Weather Forecasting and Research (SAFAR) under India's Ministry of Earth Sciences reported the air quality in first three weeks of March, the average nitrogen dioxide levels declined by 40-50% in the cities of Mumbai, Pune and Ahmadabad compared to air quality in the month of March in 2018 and 2019 (Wright, 2020).

One day Janta curfew announced by Indian Government on March 22 has give significant result in decline of traffic pollution levels. It is very essential break needed in India due o high level of air pollution enforced by nature. Last year in the month of November, 2019, many people protest against massive increase in air pollution in New Delhi due to dark yellow haze cover the city for several days. As the air pollution reaches at their high level government close the schools, restriction on vehicle and divert flight to minimize air pollutants. Now after four months, skies are clean but problem remains about those who were living in bad condition and infected with several respiratory diseases and remain contain in it. According to the WHO, peoples of old age with some pre-existing medical complications like bronchitis; asthma and

tuberculosis etc. are at higher risk of virus infection (coronavirus). Globally, around 7 million people died every year due to exposure to bad air pollutants, is pandemic condition. (WHO, 2018). A regular increase in poor air quality increases the risk of heart disease, lung cancer, and chronic and acute respiratory diseases, including asthma and tuberculosis.

CONCLUSION

Air pollution both indoor and outdoor is a major challenge for any government as it has bad impact on health of people. Central and state governments take several necessary actions time to time to minimize or control air pollution in the country. India is one of the country has highest number of respiratory disease cases in the world and also it has the world's highest number of tuberculosis patients. Complete lockdown give some relief to these patients due to decline in air pollution. However, remember that it is a temporary relief to us till industrial activities and vehicular traffic return when the lockdown is over. It is necessary for every individual who are living in this beautiful world to remember the beauty of nature and its remarkable role in the survival of all living things (both plants and animals). We have to conserve the environmental status rather than destruction.

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